

MACHINE-LEARNING ASSISTED DAMAGE STATE IDENTIFICATION FOR DETERIORATING BRIDGES

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ABSTRACT

Bridges are critical elements for the seamless functioning of our societies. Bridge closures have a direct impact on the operation of the served transport network as well as cascading consequences on the interdependent networks and systems. Despite the significant efforts that are put towards monitoring, routine maintenance and proactive restoration, bridge closures are still happening. Furthermore, many bridges have reached their end-of-life whereas at the same time are subjected to increased traffic loads and climate-change aggravated hazards. One of the main failure mechanisms when it comes to ageing prestressed concrete bridges, is the deterioration of their material properties and in particular the creep and shrinkage of concrete as well as the corrosion of tendons. Especially the damage of tendons is an exceptionally challenging source of deterioration to detect, since tendons are not always easily accessible, and their state is not interpretable without invasive inspections. This is a capability gap that eventually leads to the problem being unnoticed until large deflections are observed, or a catastrophic failure occurs—in many cases with little warning.

To address the aforementioned problem and facilitate the implementation of an early reactive protocol, a novel machine learning-driven approach for undertaking a first-order bridge damage state assessment was developed and demonstrated on the basis of a case-study. The case-study was selected to be a landmark balanced cantilever bridge located in the North-West of Greece that was recently closed to undergo structural interventions due to large deflections that were observed on its balanced cantilever deck. The methodology was built upon the development of a finite element model of the bridge and the evaluation of the deck deflections. In doing so, several plausible damage patterns were considered that account for deterioration in the concrete Young's modulus and tendon losses due to corrosion. Through analysing bridge samples reflecting variable damage conditions, a dataset of structural responses was generated, and drift-based fragility functions were obtained. The database developed was then exploited as a training set, to enable, via utilising the k-Nearest Neighbours machine learning algorithm, a rapid damage state identification for the investigated bridge should the deflections of its deck and the concrete Young's modulus are known. The novelty of the proposed methodology is its ability to interpret vertical deflections, associated with tendon loss, into a bridge damage level without having to engage thorough inspections that are usually not practically feasible during routine inspections or continuous monitoring.